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Mental toughness among International and National para-badminton players

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Background: Mental toughness is an important psychological characteristic in sports that determines the performance and achievement of an athlete. Para-badminton athletes have extra physical as well as social challenges, hence mental resilience becomes all the more important. This research investigates differences in mental toughness among international and national para-badminton athletes based on four factors: control, commitment, challenge, and confidence.

Materials and Methods: 20 para-badminton players (10 international and 10 national) were chosen randomly from the 6th National Para-Badminton Championship 2023-24. The Mental Toughness Questionnaire (MTQ-18) of Clough *et al.* (2002) was used to measure mental toughness. Data was analysed using descriptive statistics, the Shapiro-Wilk test, Levene's test, and an independent t-test (Mann-Whitney U test for non-normally distributed data) at a level of 0.05 significance.

Results: The results showed that international para-badminton athletes exhibited much greater control of emotions and pressure ($p = 0.011$) than national players. No significant difference was observed between the two groups in commitment ($p = 0.846$), challenge ($p = 0.291$), confidence ($p = 0.249$), and overall mental toughness ($p = 0.566$).

Conclusion: The research identifies that the international para-badminton players have higher emotional and pressure control, most probably because of being used to high-level competitions. The other dimensions of mental toughness were comparable between both groups. The findings highlight the importance of psychological training camps to increase the mental toughness of national-level players so as to assist their graduation to international competitions. Longitudinal studies and interventions should be studied in the future to establish mental toughness in para-badminton players.

Keywords: Para-badminton, mental strength, psychological resilience, emotional regulation, athlete performance, sports psychology

Introduction

Mental toughness is a valuable psychological characteristic of sports, most often determining athletes' performance and success rates. It particularly matters in para-badminton and badminton, in which sportswomen and men must exhibit enhanced levels of concentration, determination, and resilience under pressure (Gucciardi *et al.*, 2014) ^[5]. Mental toughness allows athletes to consistently perform despite adverse conditions, defeats, and tremendous competition. It is considered one of the important psychological skills necessary to achieve maximal performance in intense sporting competitions (Jones *et al.*, 2007) ^[4]. Athletes are presented with unique physical and psychological demands in para-badminton, so mental toughness is much more essential.

Para-badminton players, unlike non-disabled badminton players, must contend with additional physical limitations, social prejudices, and adaptability factors while maintaining high performance (Cowden, 2016) ^[2]. The ability to manage stress, to be motivated, and to be confident in the face of adversity is crucial for achieving success at the national and international levels. The evidence suggests that highly mentally tough players demonstrate greater resilience, concentration, and competitive pressure management (Mahoney *et al.*, 2014) ^[5]. (Clough *et al.*, 2002) ^[1]. defined mental toughness in four primary dimensions: challenge, commitment, control, and confidence. These aspects assist in knowing how sports performers manage adversity, remain committed to their aim, manage emotions, and uphold self-belief. Elevated mental toughness has been linked with higher sports performance, greater stress management, and superior coping processes (Jones *et al.*, 2007) ^[4]. Research has found that international sportspeople tend to have greater mental toughness than national-level sportspeople because they are used to competing under more challenging situations and

intense training regimens (Gucciardi *et al.*, 2014) [5]. International para-badminton players will also improve their mental toughness as they play against international-standard competitors and encounter varied sports conditions. On the other hand, national-level players might lack the same exposure, which may hamper their scores on mental toughness.

This research aims to examine the variations in mental toughness between international and national para-badminton players. By comparing their scores on the four factors of mental toughness, the study attempts to offer information on para-badminton athletes' psychological strengths and weaknesses. Knowing these variations can contribute to formulating training programs and psychological interventions that increase mental toughness and performance in para-badminton players across different levels.

Objectives

1. To compare the Total mental toughness between national and international para-badminton players.
2. To assess the status and compare control between national and international para-badminton players.
3. To analyze the status and compare commitment between national and international para-badminton players.
4. To evaluate the status and compare the challenges faced by national and international para-badminton players.
5. To examine the status and comparison of confidence

between national and international para-badminton players.

Methodology

1. **Sample:** 10 International Para-Badminton Players and 10 National Players of the 6th National Championship 2023-24 held at Jrd, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, participated in the research.
2. **Sampling Technique:** The Research study used a Random sampling technique by the researcher to select the sample from the 6th National Para-Badminton Championship 2023-24.
3. **Questionnaire:** (Clough *et al.*, 2002) [1] Mental Toughness Questionnaire (MTQ-18) was utilized to evaluate mental toughness across the four dimensions of Challenge, Commitment, Control, and Confidence.
4. **Procedure:** The researcher explains in front of the selected subjects the procedure and direction of accomplishing the questionnaire so that the maximum data can be obtained from the selected subjects on the objective of the study.
5. **Statistical Techniques:** Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and the Shapiro-Wilk test were used to check the data's normality, Levene's Test was used to check the equality of variance of the group, and inferential statistics (independent t-test) were applied to compare groups based on the objectives. The level of significance is at 0.05.

Results

Table 1: The Shapiro-Wilk normality test results for five variables - Control, commitment, challenge, confidence, and total mental toughness

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)		
	W	p
Control	0.963	0.598
Commitment	0.856	0.007
Challenge	0.956	0.468
Confidence	0.956	0.465
Tot_Men_Tough	0.959	0.521

Table 1 above shows that the Shapiro-Wilk normality test results for five variables - Control, commitment, challenge, confidence, and total mental toughness - are shown in the table. The test is given as the p-value, with $p > 0.05$

indicating normal distribution. All except Commitment variables show normal distribution since commitment has a p-value of 0.007, suggesting that it is abnormal.

Table 2: Levene's test for homogeneity of variances for five variables: Control, Commitment, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness

Homogeneity of Variances Test (Levene's)				
	F	df	df2	p
Control	0.034	1	18	0.854
Commitment	0.126	1	18	0.726
Challenge	0.006	1	18	0.935
Confidence	2.808	1	18	0.111
Tot_Men_Tough	1.497	1	18	0.237

Table 2 shows the output of Levene's test for homogeneity of variances for five variables: Control, Commitment, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness. The test gives the p-value, and $p > 0.05$ implies equal variances.

The p-values of all variables are more than 0.05, which means that homogeneity of variances is preserved in all groups.

Table 3: Results of the Independent Samples T-Test for Control, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness

Independent Samples T-Test				
		Statistic	df	p
Control	Student's t	2.850	18.0	0.011
Challenge	Student's t	1.089	18.0	0.291
Confidence	Student's t	-1.191	18.0	0.249
Total Mental Toughness	Student's t	0.584	18.0	0.566

Table no 3 shows the results of the Independent Samples T-Test for Control, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness. The t-statistic, degrees of freedom (df), and p-value are given, and a $p \leq 0.05$ value signifies a statistically significant difference between groups. The Control variable

is only significant ($p = 0.011$), with the others not being significant, and it indicates no statistically significant differences among groups for Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness.

Table 4: Independent Samples T-Test

		Statistic	df	p
Commitment	Mann-Whitney U	47.0		0.846

From Tables 1 and 2, researchers found that one of the variables, commitment data, is not normal but has homogeneity in equal variance. The researcher chose to use

the Mann-Whitney U test as a non-parametric alternative to the t-test, and the p-value (0.846) indicates no significant difference between groups.

Table 5: Group Descriptives

	Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	P	Interpretation
Control	I_B_P	10	18.90	19.00	2.60	0.823	0.011	Significant Difference
	N_B_P	10	15.80	15.50	2.25	0.712		
Commitment	I_B_P	10	8.70	8.00	2.41	0.761	0.846	No Significant Difference
	N_B_P	10	8.50	7.50	2.17	0.687		
Challenge	I_B_P	10	12.30	12.00	1.49	0.473	0.291	No Significant Difference
	N_B_P	10	11.50	11.00	1.78	0.563		
Confidence	I_B_P	10	27.40	27.50	3.92	1.240	0.249	No Significant Difference
	N_B_P	10	29.10	29.00	2.23	0.706		
Tot_Men_Tough	I_B_P	10	66.40	65.50	5.93	1.875	0.566	No Significant Difference
	N_B_P	10	65.10	66.00	3.78	1.197		

N.B: I_B_P- International Badminton Players N_B_P- National Badminton Players

From the above-consolidated table no 4, it has been found that the only significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found in the Control dimension, indicating that international players

exhibit significantly better control over emotions and pressure than national players. Other dimensions, including Commitment, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness, did not show statistically significant differences.

Plot 1: Represent the Mean & Median of Control on Para International and National Badminton Player

Fig 1: Represent the Mean & SD of Control on Para International and National Badminton Players

Control: From the above-consolidated table no 5, it has been found that the international players have a higher mean (18.9 & 19.00) than national players (15.80 & 15.50), indicating they manage emotions and pressures better. The

only significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found in the Control dimension, indicating that international players exhibit significantly better control over emotions and pressure than national players.

Plot 2: Represent the Mean & Median of Commitment on Para International and National Badminton Players

Fig 2: Represent the Mean & SD of Commitment on Para International and National Badminton Players

Commitment: From the above-consolidated table no 5, it has been found that the means for both groups are similar (8.70 for international, 8.50 for national) and P-Value is

0.846 > 0.05 suggesting that no significant difference was found in the Commitment Dimension.

Plot 3: Represent the Mean & Median of Challenge on Para International and National Badminton Players

Fig 3: Represent the Mean & SD of Challenge on Para International and National Badminton Players

Challenge: From the above-consolidated table no 5, it has been found that the international players have a slightly higher mean (12.30) than national players (11.50),

suggesting a greater tendency to embrace challenges but P-Value is 0.291 > 0.05 suggesting that no significant difference was found in the Challenge Dimension.

Plot 4: Represent the Mean & Median of Confidence on Para International and National Badminton Players

Fig 4: Represent the Mean & SD of Confidence on Para International and National Badminton Players

Confidence: From the above-consolidated table no 5, it has been found that, Interestingly, national players report slightly higher confidence (29.1) compared to international players (27.40). However, the variation (SD = 3.92 for

international, 2.23 for national) suggests that international players have a wider range of confidence levels. No Significant difference was found in the Confidence Dimension.

Plot 5: Represent the Mean & Median of Total Mental Toughness of Para International and National Badminton Players

Fig 5: Represent the Mean & SD of Total Mental Toughness of Para International and National Badminton Players

Total Mental Toughness: From the above-consolidated table no 5, it has been found that international players have a slightly higher total mental toughness mean (66.4) than national players (65.1). The standard deviation is greater for

international players (5.93), suggesting more individual differences in mental toughness. No Significant difference was found in Total Mental Toughness between Para International and National Badminton Players.

Dimension	International (M±SD)	National (M±SD)	t-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
Control	18.9±2.60	15.8±2.25	2.85	0.011	Significant Difference (P < 0.05)
Commitment	8.7±2.41	8.5±2.17	0.20	0.848	No Significant Difference
Challenge	12.7±2.50	11.5±1.78	1.24	0.232	No Significant Difference
Confidence	27.6±4.38	29.1±2.23	-0.97	0.347	No Significant Difference
Total Mental Toughness	66.4±5.93	65.1±3.78	0.58	0.566	No Significant Difference

From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that the only significant difference (p < 0.05) was found in the Control dimension, indicating that international players exhibit significantly better control over emotions and

pressure than national players. Other dimensions, including Commitment, Challenge, Confidence, and Total Mental Toughness, did not show statistically significant differences.

Fig 6: Represent the Mean & SD of Control on Para International and National Badminton Players

Control: From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that the International players have a higher mean (18.9) than national players (15.8), indicating they manage emotions and pressures better. The standard deviation is slightly higher for international players (2.60), showing

more variation in responses. The only significant difference (p < 0.05) was found in the Control dimension, indicating that international players exhibit significantly better control over emotions and pressure than national players.

Fig 7: Represent the Mean & SD of Commitment on Para International and National Badminton Players

Commitment: From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that the means for both groups are similar (8.7 for international, 8.5 for national), suggesting comparable dedication levels. Standard deviations (2.41 and

2.17) indicate moderate variation in responses. No Significant difference was found in the Commitment Dimension.

Fig 8: Represent the Mean & SD of Challenge on Para International and National Badminton Players

Challenge: From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that the International players have a slightly higher mean (12.7) than national players (11.5), suggesting a greater tendency to embrace challenges. The standard

deviation is higher for international players (2.50), indicating more variability in responses. No Significant difference was found in the Challenge Dimension.

Fig 9: Represent the Mean & SD of Confidence on Para International and National Badminton Players

Confidence: From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that, Interestingly, national players report slightly higher confidence (29.1) compared to international players (27.6). However, the variation (SD = 4.38 for

international, 2.23 for national) suggests that international players have a wider range of confidence levels. No Significant difference was found in the Confidence Dimension.

Fig 10: Represent the Mean & SD of Total Mental Toughness of Para International and National Badminton Players

Total Mental Toughness: From the above-consolidated table no 1, it has been found that International players have a slightly higher total mental toughness mean (66.4) than national players (65.1). The standard deviation is greater for

international players (5.93), suggesting more individual differences in mental toughness. No Significant difference was found in Total Mental Toughness between Para International and National Badminton Players.

Fig 11: Represent the Mean & SD of Control, Commitment, Challenge, and Confidence on Para International and National Badminton Players

Discussion and Findings

The findings indicate that para-badminton players worldwide are likely to have greater levels of control, likely due to their high levels of competitive experience and exposure to high-pressure situations (Mahoney *et al.*, 2014)^[5]. Differences in other facets, including commitment, challenge, and confidence, were not statistically significant, indicating that national players have similar levels of resilience in these factors. Prior studies have shown that experience, training, and exposure to competition play a crucial role in shaping mental toughness in athletes (Jones *et al.*, 2007)^[4].

The superior control among international players aligns with studies linking elite performance to emotional regulation and situational mastery (Jones *et al.*, 2007)^[4]. The lack of

differences in other dimensions suggests that para-athletes at both levels exhibit comparable resilience and dedication, possibly due to shared adversities in para-sports (Martin, 2012). However, the marginal advantage in control for international players may reflect advanced coping strategies honed through global competitions.

Exposure to diverse competitive environments allows international players to build stronger psychological resilience, which is crucial for consistent performance at elite levels (Gucciardi *et al.*, 2014)^[5]

However, the other three dimensions—commitment, challenge, and confidence—failed to reveal differences between the two groups. This may imply that both international and national players reflect similar strengths in commitment and belief in themselves. Existing studies

indicate that athletes at all levels of competition could have similar motivational traits, but those at international levels tend to adapt their coping mechanisms and emotional resilience based on experience (Jones *et al.*, 2007) ^[4]. Overall, the research emphasizes the role of mental toughness in para-badminton and recommends the adoption of structured psychological training to assist national players in boosting their mental resilience at the international level.

Conclusion

This research concludes that para-badminton international players have significantly higher control levels, which could be due to exposure to high-level competitions. Yet, commitment, challenge, and confidence levels seem comparatively equal between the two groups. These results indicate the importance of specific psychological training programs to improve mental toughness in national players. Longitudinal studies and intervention measures could be studied further in future research to better develop mental toughness in para-badminton players at all levels.

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